

CONSUMER SATISFACTION ON PATANJALI PRODUCTS

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Abstract:

In the present scenario maintaining good health is considered as a difficult task. As consumers are aware of chemical preservatives added in the products they consume, they are moving towards natural and Ayurvedic products. This study is focused on Satisfaction of consumers on Patanjali products in Pollachi Taluk. There is a need to know the level of satisfaction on Patanjali products which has tremendous growth when compared to other Ayurvedic products. Primary data were collected through 192 questionnaires from Patanjali consumers and the collected data is analysed using simple percentage and chi-square. The study reveals that the consumers are satisfied by Patanjali products as it is chemical free. Majority of the consumers are satisfied with the Patanjali products and the variables namely marital status, period of usage, amount spent, and suggestion to purchase are associated with the level of satisfaction on patanjali products.

Key Words: Ayurveda, Patanjali Products & Consumers Level of Satisfaction

Introduction:

Life of human being depends on healthy life. Ayurveda helps to lead a healthy life. India is well known for its traditional medical system ‘Ayurveda’, the oldest medical system which goes back nearly 5000 years. Patanjali Ayurved Ltd is one of the herbal and ayurvedic company with tremendous growth and is one of the fastest growing FMCG firm in India. Patanjali Ayurved Ltd, a company registered under company’s act 1956 with its registered office at New Delhi and manufacturing plants in Haridwar and Uttarkhand. Initially it was formed as a private company on 13th January 2006 and later converted as public ltd company on June 25th 2007. Acharya Balakrishna is the founder of Patanjali Ayurved Ltd and he owns 92% shares and balance 8% is owned by Sarwan and Sunita Podder, a Scotland based non-resident Indian couple. Baba Ramdevji is not the shareholder of this company but he played a huge part in the brand’s gaining visibility by marketing patanjali products in his yoga camps. The main aim of this company is to provide superior products at far prices. Patanjali sales reached Rs 50 billion by the end of 2016 and this company targeted to reach 100 billion by the end of 2019. The main aim of this company is to satisfy the consumers by providing products with natural ingredients. This company manufactures healthy, herb, mineral, heal care, dental care, food, cosmetics and other products. Patanjali products are sold in separate Patanjali stores and online purchase of Patanjali product is also made now possible. Patanjali products are offered at 30% discount which attracts the consumers. As it is made of raw materials directly purchased from natural plants there is no side effects after using this products. This is the main reason for the consumers to move towards Patanjali products.

Review of Literature:

The studies which are carried out in India and abroad are reviewed in the following paragraph. Rupali Khanna (2015) reveals that reasonable price and problem curing are the factors that determines customers satisfaction towards Patanjali products. S. Anupriya (2017) identify that all the respondents prefer the Patanjali product as it is chemical free and they are satisfied with the quality and price of the product. Chandiralekha and Dr. Hamsalakshmi (2016) finds that most of the consumers prefer Patanjali product as it is chemical free and also the customers are satisfied with price and quality of patanjali products. Prof. Brijesh Singh and Dr. R.K. Gopal (2016) states that ‘Natural products with affordable prices’ and ‘Swadeshi Make’ (make in India) are the main reason for the growth of Patanjali Ayurved Ltd. G. Satheesh Raju and R. Rahul (2016) states ‘Price’ plays a significant role in consumers buying behavior for Patanjali products.

Statement of the Problem:

The satisfied customers are the one who creates value to the company. They remain with the company, refer their friends and relatives and prefer to repurchase the same products. Patanjali brand marked its entry in to herbal market and FMCG in 2012. From then onwards Dabur (launched 1884), Himalaya (launched 1930), Amrutanjan (launched 1893), VICCO (launched 1952) etc are facing intimidation from a home – grown and a absolutely “Swadeshi” competitor, Patanjali Ayurved Limited. The business prospects of Patanjali amounts to a \$20 billion ready market and its gigantic growth rate would be \$5 trillion in 2050 worldwide. To attain this growth rate the company has to retain its existing customers and also should capture the minds of new customers. This will happen only if it satisfies the needs of the customers. In this regard, there raises the question: What are determinants of consumers level of satisfaction on Patanjali products.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the usage of Patanjali products
- ✓ To ascertain the determinants of consumer’s level of satisfaction on Patanjali products

Research Methodology:

This study is based on primary data which is collected through well framed questionnaire issued to 200 consumers of Patanjali products in Pollachi Taluk. Of the total 200 questionnaires issued, 18 found to be incomplete and 192 questionnaires were taken for analysis. Convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sample consumers of Patanjali products. The data collected have been analyzed using Simple Percentage and Chi-Square.

Findings of the Study:

Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Consumers of Patanjali Products – Simple Percentage:

The findings relating to socio-economic profile of customers namely, area of residence, age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, number of earning members in the family, number of non-earning members in the family, number of total members in the family, monthly income, source of awareness, period of usage and amount spend for purchase are presented below

Table 1

Factors	No. of Respondents N=192	Factors	No. of Respondents N=192
Area of Residence		No. of Earning Members in the Family	
Rural	116 (60.42)	1	
Urban	47 (24.48)	2	66 (34.38)
Semi Urban	29 (15.10)	Above 2	104 (54.12)
			22 (11.50)
Age		No. of Non-Earning Members in the family	
Up to 20 yrs	92 (47.92)	Less than or equal to 1	58 (30.21)
21-40 yrs	69 (35.94)	2	90 (46.87)
41-60 yrs	26 (13.54)	Above 2	44 (22.92)
Above 60 yrs	5 (2.60)		
Gender		Total No. of Members	
Female	131 (68.22)	Less than or equal to 3	71 (36.98)
Male	61 (31.78)	4	96 (50.00)
		Above 4	25 (13.02)
Marital Status		Status in the family	
Married	78 (40.63)	Head	31 (16.14)
Un married	114 (59.37)	Member	161 (83.86)
Educational Qualification		Monthly Income	
Un-Educated	2 (1.04)	Up to Rs.10000	48 (25)
Up to SSLC	13 (6.77)	Rs.10000 to Rs.20000	14 (7.30)
HSC	20 (10.41)	Rs.25000 to Rs. 50000	10 (5.20)
UG	115 (59.90)	Above Rs. 50000	8 (4.16)
PG	29 (15.10)	Nil	112 (58.34)
Others	13 (6.78)		
Occupation		Source of Awareness	
Agriculturist	15 (7.82)	Friends	40 (20.84)
Self-Employed	26 (13.54)	Relatives	24 (12.5)
Professional	4 (2.08)	Colleagues	8 (4.16)
Govt.Employee	9 (4.69)	Advertisement	103 (53.65)
Pvt.Employee	28 (14.58)	Family members	16 (8.33)
Others	110 (57.29)	Existing customers	1 (0.52)
Period of Usage		Amount spent	
Less than 6 months	97 (50.53)	Below Rs.500	110 (57.30)
1 Year	64 (33.33)	Rs. 500- Rs.1000	58 (30.20)
1-5 Years	22 (11.45)	Above Rs. 5000	24 (12.5)
More than 5 years	9 (4.69)		

It is clear from Table-1 that out of 192 respondents, 116 respondents resides in rural area, 92 respondents age are up to 20 years, 131 are female respondents, 114 respondents are unmarried, 115 respondents are UG holders, 110 respondents are others like students, 104 respondents have 2 earning members in the family, 90 respondents have 2 non -earning members in the family, 112 respondents have no income as they are

students, house wife, 103 respondents are aware of products through advertisement, 97 respondents are using the products less than 6 months, and 110 respondents spent below Rs. 500 for the purchase of Patanjali products

Level of Satisfaction on Patanjali Products - Chi-Square:

Fifteen variables namely area of residence, age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, number of earning members in the family, number of non-earning members in the family, total number of members in the family, status in the family, monthly income, source of awareness, period of usage, amount spent, level of usage and purchase decision have been selected in order to test whether there really exists any association between each of the variable and level of satisfaction. Chi-square test has been applied to test the association. Level of significance chosen are one and five percent level

Table 2

Associated	Not Associated
Marital status	Area of residence
Period of usage	Age
Amount spent	Gender
Suggestions to purchase	Education qualification
	No of earning members
	No of non-earning members
	Total no of members in the family
	Status
	Monthly income
	Level of usage
	Purchase Decision

Table 2 reveals that out of 15 variables, four variables namely marital status, period of usage, amount spent, and suggestion to purchase are associated with the level of satisfaction on patanjali products. The variables such as area of residence, age, gender, education qualification, occupation, number of earning members in the family, number of non-earning members, total number of members in the family, status in the family, monthly income, level of usage and purchase decision are not associated with consumers level of satisfaction on Patanjali products.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Frequent Product offers to be given
- ✓ Ingredients of the products should be made clear in the package to satisfy the customers
- ✓ Patanjali stores should be opened in rural areas
- ✓ Quality of the products should be checked frequently
- ✓ Attractive advertisements to be posted in many social media
- ✓ Avoid selling other local brand products in Patanjali retail stores

Conclusion:

Living healthy is the wish of each and every human being in the world. Recently there are many news which are not positive with regard to the products that we use both internally and externally. This have made the consumers to shift to herbal and ayurvedic products and with this context the study has been done to identify the consumers satisfaction on the Patanjali Ayurveda products. The study reveals that majority of the consumers are satisfied with the Patanjali products and the variables namely marital status, period of usage, amount spent, and suggestion to purchase are associated with the level of satisfaction on Patanjali products.

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